

DESIGN CONSIDERATIONS FOR COMPOSITE MATERIALS

Scala Lecture

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PREFACE

The following is a modified transcript of the author's lecture presented at the ICCM. Its emphasis is upon discussion of concepts. It is not in the form of a formal paper, and it does not contain a list of references. The examples presented are drawn from the work of the author and his colleagues at MSC. The author expresses his appreciation to his colleagues, particularly to Zvi Hashin and Norris F. Dow, for their assistance in formulating this lecture.

INTRODUCTION

It is significant to note that we have gathered here in Toronto to interchange views on a range of technical subjects whose common theme is the material of construction. This is not a conference of structural analysts, of material scientists, of polymer chemists, of designers, or of material suppliers. But rather, it is a conference which is unavoidably interdisciplinary. This is as it must be, because utilization of composites requires the simultaneous design of both the material and the product. Success in this endeavor requires the breaking down of barriers built over many years between individual technology groups. It brings me personal satisfaction to present this first Scala lecture, as one of my earliest attempts to break down these barriers was in collaboration with Pete Scala some 20 years ago.

Dr. Scala at that time was the head of the materials department at the then new, high technology organization called the Avco Research and Advanced Development Division. I was the Deputy Director of the missile program office. Our problem at that time was to develop a material which could withstand the extreme thermal environment of missile re-entry after flight over intercontinental range. It was necessary to turn from the heavy materials, which function as re-entry heat sinks, to the brittle ceramic ablators which shield the cargo by heat absorption during phase changes. Thermal shock was one of the critical problems for that application. Thus structural analysts and material scientists had to collaborate in order to provide a solution. The result was a metal honeycomb reinforced ceramic called Avcoite, which provided the desired combination of high thermal performance and excellent resistance to thermal shock. For all of us on that project, we became involved for the first

time in that as yet unnamed technology which we now call composite materials. Then, as now, an understanding of the interactions between different phases in a multiphase material was imperative to the development of a successful product. From that start, Dr. Scala went on to a university and government career which eventually brought him to his present involvement in the commercial utilization of advanced composites.

These have been an exciting 20 years. However, the problems remain in many cases as they were at the start; problems of integrating the needs of multiple disciplines; problems of understanding that these composite materials are unique and should be used in ways which recognize their uniqueness. These 20 years have brought us to the threshold of a time in which requirements for the efficient utilization of materials will lead to an ever increasing role for advanced fiber composites.

For some years we have been poised at, or perhaps on or even slightly over, the threshold of substantial commercial exploitation of composites. Clearly now we are moving across that threshold. Yet, we do this at a time when the technology of composites is still under development. Hence, it is important that we proceed with a dual approach. On the one hand, we must use conservative design techniques. At the same time, we must have continued R&D to resolve the critical unknowns. In other words, it is necessary to identify the problem areas, avoid them in our designs, test extensively for those we cannot avoid, and treat the remaining problems in our R&D work.

PROPERTY EVALUATION

In this lecture, I wish to identify our analysis capabilities for composites, to define the critical problem areas, and to describe rational design approaches. I will focus on those areas in which composites differ from metals. I will emphasize the existence of design approaches that enable us to use these materials in a reliable fashion at the present time, while we continue to study those factors which we do not fully understand.

We are concerned with commercial utilization of composites. Such utilization is motivated by the potential for: weight reduction, improved strength and stiffness, and hence performance, and most importantly, longer life and lower manufacturing cost. In order to attain the full potential of these materials, the design process must place emphasis upon the need to minimize fabrication costs. Minimization of part count, and integration of various types of sub-structural elements are examples of such an approach, strongly influenced by the commercial developments. In our design with these materials, we must define requirements just as we do for metals. This includes functional requirements such as mechanical, thermal, electrical and chemical properties, and economic requirements; and also we must establish performance objectives. The design process results in the definition of the selected material, and of the structural configuration, and of the fabrication process. The difference for composites, the uniqueness of composites, is in the need to obtain both structural configuration and material configuration simultaneously, as suggested in figure 1. The various factors which influence the design process must lead us to an understanding of how to configure a known material, after we select its constituents. The designer must identify a material configuration, for example, a laminate containing one or more oriented fiber systems, and at the same time configure the structure in a way which can exploit the unique properties of that composite material.

The fact that we have such a wide range of composite materials to choose from, as suggested in figure 2 by the stress-strain curves for a sampling of the available commercial fibers, presents us with an initial issue of concern.

Figure 1. Factors Influencing the Design of Composite Materials and Structures.

There are a large number of candidate constituent materials. There are an even larger number of material configuration variables including amount of fibers, orientation of fibers, combination of fibers, etc. This suggests the possible need for extensive testing in order to characterize these materials. Thus, we are faced with two possible alternatives: one, to use testing for the basic ply properties and to thoroughly characterize this basic material, be it a unidirectional fiber composite prepreg, a molding compound, a fabric impregnated with a polymer, etc. In this approach one works from the measured pro-

Figure 2. Stress-Strain Diagrams of Various Contemporary Fibers.

perties of these basic materials, utilizing reliable analysis methods, in order to calculate preliminary design properties for any of the desired configurations.

An alternative to this approach is to focus on a limited number of well-characterized materials; for example, a quasi-isotropic laminate. However, this design approach cannot be successful. I believe we must recognize that we cannot rationally constrain the number of alternate material configurations which will be utilized. Thus, although some fiber materials will grow in popularity, they will not be used exclusively. It is true that we may expect that increased market volume will yield an associated decrease in price. This decrease in price may make a given material even more attractive for other applications so that it is reasonable to expect that a near term trend will be to reduce the number of fibers available in the marketplace. However, the important design consideration is that, if anything, the number of material configurations will constantly increase through the use of hybrids and other innovative material construction forms. Hence, we must choose the path of understanding the properties of the basic material and using analysis methods in order to perform our preliminary design studies. These analyses methods for composites will be more complex than they are for metals. Hence, it is important that we choose the right method and understand the basis for the choice.

An issue here is the determination of whether we use a macroscopic or a microscopic viewpoint. We must, of course, at various times use both. The design engineer must recognize which is appropriate in a particular problem. In general, the objective is to establish effective properties which can be used in conventional analysis methods. Thus, the design objective is to work from the properties of the basic material, frequently a unidirectional fiber composite prepreg, and obtain, via analysis methods, the material properties to be used for a variety of candidate laminates. For example, as illustrated in figure 3, we may start with the elastic constants of the unidirectional

Figure 3. Representation of the Analytical Procedure for Obtaining Laminate Physical Properties.

material and determine the extensional and bending stiffnesses of the laminate for use in structural stress analysis. In this area, the state of the art in analysis methods is excellent. We have the capability to make the transformation from ply properties to laminate properties for elastic constants, for thermal expansion characteristics, for thermal and electrical conductivity, for magnetic properties, and for viscoelastic properties. The methods exist; yet even in a very well developed area, such as elastic properties, we must recognize that these materials are unique and if the designer is not careful problems may arise. This is illustrated by elastic analysis of the two rather simple laminate configurations shown in figure 4. The first material is a

Figure 4. Strain Distribution in Unsymmetric Laminates for a Central Uniaxial Membrane Load.

0/90 cross ply material of graphite/epoxy which we refer to as being unsymmetric because of the lack of symmetry about the middle plane. The second material is a protected symmetric laminate in which the symmetric laminate has over it a thin layer of glass fabric for protection against surface abrasion. Shown on the right in figure 4 is the strain distribution that results from the application of a central load to these laminates. There is a substantial difference in strain across the thickness of the laminate, even for these relatively simple configurations, which are not far from mid-plane symmetry. Both undesirable deformations and difficulty of failure prediction result from these asymmetries. Hence, the design approach here is to utilize symmetric and balanced laminates. The R&D need is to upgrade some of our structural analysis tools, such as the finite element codes, so that we can be more arbitrary in our choice of material configurations and still be able to exploit its desirable properties. This simple example serves to illustrate that, although our understanding is incomplete, it is not impeding progress in the design area. This is a general characteristic of the state of the art of composites today. Sound design approaches do exist to circumvent problems which we recognize.

Figure 5. Distributed Fiber Breaks at 94.9% Failure Load

FAILURE EVALUATION

A more critical problem is associated with the question of strength analysis in composites. The problem results from the diversity of failure mechanisms in composites. For example, figure 5 shows a number of distributed fiber breaks observed photoelastically in a unidirectional fiber composite being subjected to a tensile load in a horizontal direction. The dispersed points of damage throughout the material are characteristic of the failure mode of a fiber composite in tension. These damage sites continue to grow in size and number as the loading upon the composite is increased, finally leading to tensile failure. In compression, there is a very different failure mechanism. Figure 6 presents a photoelastic observation of isolated fibers embedded in an epoxy matrix under compressive strain. Here a microbuckling phenomenon

Figure 6. Photoelastic Stress Patterns for Two Individual E-Glass Fibers Embedded in an Epoxy Matrix Showing Small Wavelength Buckle Patterns

can be seen in the form of a waviness or instability similar to that of a column on an elastic foundation. The modes of failure, in tension and compression, are very different. Hence, it is reasonable to expect that combined stress problems will be complex for these materials. Understanding the mode of failure under combined stresses is indeed a problem. However, it has been observed and demonstrated that a polynomial function of the various stress components, used with experimental data for uniaxial stress states, yields a very good design tool for predicting what happens in a unidirectional fiber composite material subjected to combined stresses. The problem is that when we go to a laminate, although we can calculate the stress and strain state which would exist in a ply at the time that failure would be predicted for the

purely unidirectional material, we do not know what will happen subsequent to that at higher stress levels in a composite laminate. That is, the in-situ properties of the unidirectional material differ from the coupon properties. Hence, we can calculate first ply failure but we must explore the problem of strength after damage initiation.

Figure 7. Representation of Load Transfer Around Ply Cracks in a Cross-Ply Laminate

The formation of an axial crack (parallel to the fibers) in a 90° ply subjected to load in a 0° direction is suggested schematically in figure 7. When such a crack occurs in a unidirectional material loaded transversely to the fiber direction it means failure of the coupon. In a composite it means localized stress concentrations and interlaminar stress transfer around the damage. Thus, beyond the point of first ply failure, the laminate may retain its load carrying capability. This effect is illustrated in figure 8 for the case of a $+45^\circ$ laminate subjected to a uniaxial stress state. The solid curve is the stress-strain curve to laminate failure. The dashed curve is displaced slightly to indicate the point of predicted first ply failure. It is seen that there is a substantial strain capability retained beyond the point of damage onset.

Figure 8. Stress-Strain Curve for an Angle-Ply Laminate.

This is a problem area in which predicted performance is strongly influenced by matrix properties. The role of matrix properties may properly be regarded as being relatively unexplored, particularly when compared with the work that has been done with fibers. Yet, matrix properties not only influence strength characteristics, but they can have an important, indeed a dominant effect upon the fatigue characteristics of a laminate or upon those properties which are associated with interlaminar effects or environmental ef-

fects. Furthermore, the role of the matrix in determining fabrication feasibility and costs through such characteristics as cure time, cure temperature, and storage requirements, etc., is a very important area for improving composite materials, where the major improvement can be lowered cost. In order to consider changing matrix characteristics, one can suggest the possibility of alleviating some problems by going to a lower stiffness matrix material. This requires consideration as to what happens to the major inplane characteristics.

Figure 9. Laminate Failure Surface for In-Plane Stresses on a Quasi-Isotropic Laminate

Laminate failure surfaces for a quasi-isotropic graphite/epoxy composite are shown in figure 9. The failure surfaces are for combined membrane stresses in two different directions. The dashed curve is the maximum strain failure envelope for first ply failure. The solid curve is the result of fiber failure. The large region between these two surfaces indicates the potentially limiting effect of low transverse and shear strengths of the individual plies, hence the limiting effect of the matrix properties. Figure 10 shows changes in the failure surface that result from a reduction in the matrix modulus by a factor of two while keeping constant the allowable strength value. Thus, the strain to failure is increased. The effect of this change in matrix properties upon the properties in the fiber direction has been estimated as causing approximately a 20% decrease in compressive and tensile strength. Thus, the effects of this are to reduce the fiber failure surface (solid curve) and greatly expand the transverse/shear failure surface (dashed curve). As a result of this change, the matrix property is much less critical to structural strength. Changes in matrix properties offer the potential for improved performance. In any event, our existing design approach is adequate. Preliminary design failure calculations should be based both upon first ply failure and upon fiber direction failure. It is necessary to recognize that there are two different characteristic stress levels in these materials, just as a yield stress and an ultimate stress characterize metallic materials. These stress levels must be used with different factors of safety. When the preliminary design phase identifies the selected laminate (or a limited number of candidate laminates) testing will be necessary in order to verify predicted proper-

Figure 10. Laminate Failure Surface for a Composite with a Modified Matrix Material.

ties of the selected design laminate.

Another important area for design consideration is thermal stress. Our capability in the area of thermal stress enables us to do elastic analysis for temperature-dependent properties. The concerns in the area of thermal stress are the possible nonlinear effects associated with large temperature changes. This can be illustrated by some recent test results developed for graphite/polyimide composites. Table 1 shows experimental thermal expansion coefficients for the range 70° to 065°F along with the much larger number associated with reversing the direction of the same temperature change. An existing analysis based upon the treatment of nonlinear transverse stress-strain char-

Table 1. Nonlinear Effects Occurring upon Thermal Expansion of Graphite/Polyimide Laminates.

AVERAGE THERMAL EXPANSION (μ IN/IN °F)			AVERAGE THERMAL EXPANSION (μ IN/IN °F)		
	TEMPERATURE RANGE		STRESS-FREE TEMP.		
	70° to -65°F	-65° to 70°F	70°F	300°F	
EXP.	0.6	3.5	2.6	0.6	
ANAL.	0.6	1.6	1.3	0.6	

EFFECTS OF HIGH PLY STRESSES

EFFECTS OF STRESS RELAXATION

acteristics supports this phenomenon although the analytical values do not predict as large an effect as the experiments show. Analysis capability is limited in this area. However, the design approach exists, namely, to use small temperature ranges and to test to demonstrate margins of safety.

Figure 11. Failure Mechanisms for Various Notched Fiber Composite Laminates under Tensile Fatigue Loading

FRACTURE AND FATIGUE

Another important design consideration is fracture. Figure 11 illustrates a variety of failure modes associated with different laminates. It is shown that a quasi-isotropic laminate fails due to the stress concentration at the hole in a fashion similar to a metallic structure. However, in general, failure modes in composite laminates will be diverse. Crack propagation will not be in a self similar fashion. Hence, the classical fracture mechanics technology developed for metals cannot easily be applied in a direct fashion to composites. One of the significant reasons for this is the existence of interlaminar stresses in composites. Particularly around a hole, as illustrated schematically in figure 12, the interlaminar normal stresses can give rise to delaminations, cracks parallel to fiber directions, and combinations of delamination and cracks. These failure mechanisms alleviate stress concentrations and prevent the transverse crack propagation from occurring.

The magnitude of the interlaminar stresses can be significant, as shown in figure 13. The interlaminar normal stress for this laminate is estimated to be as high as 15% of the in-plane applied stress which is large enough to cause a problem because of the low interlaminar normal strength. This is clearly a characteristic which distinguishes a composite from a metal. The design approach for these problems is to change the material configuration in the region of stress concentration. When manufactured holes exist in the composite, it is necessary to use different lamination patterns in the vicinity

Figure 12. Representation of Damage Regions Around a Hole in a Composite Laminate

of the holes. But also, it must be recognized that composite materials must have damage tolerance, and therefore, it must be expected that the design should be tolerant of a hole. Such a hole or crack may occur in service even in regions in which there is not a manufactured hole. Thus, we must reduce operating strain levels. The structural advantages of fiber composites are adequate to enable us to take this design penalty during the transition range when the understanding of laminate behavior is not adequate to provide us with the necessary capability for fracture prediction.

Of even greater importance with regards to stress concentrations, is the problem of fatigue in composites. Here, indeed, our understanding is limited.

Figure 13. Interlaminar Normal Stresses Around a Hole in a Composite Laminate.

However, we must be encouraged by the fact that experimental data demonstrate long lifetimes even for relatively highly stressed composite structures. Fatigue has not been demonstrated to be a critical problem. Indeed, it appears that composites are attractive from this point of view. However, they are attractive at the reduced operating strain levels and therefore there is a clear need for further understanding of fatigue. Indeed, it is important to develop a capability to understand load history effects so that we may reduce the amount of testing necessary for demonstration and certification structures.

One of the fatigue problems which is unique to composites is illustrated in figure 14. This shows initial defects of two different sizes which, under fatigue loading, experience axial cracking arresting the growth of the initial defect. The axial cracking blunts the notch tip overstress, as the applied stress is increased, and as this crack arrest mechanism grows. The growth rate for a transverse crack, or an axial crack, varies depending upon the size of the initial crack. Hence, it is quite feasible to find that the larger crack which is critical early, may subsequently become less critical than the smaller crack.

Figure 14. Damage Growth under Fatigue Loading and Resulting Change in Stress Concentration.

A possible consequence of this from a lifetime/reliability point of view is shown in figure 15. Different contributors to the initial statistical distribution of static strength may grow differently with lifetime such that the mode which is not critical in the static case (as indicated by the solid line distribution curve) for the as-manufactured coupons, may become critical late in the lifetime of the material. It is this complexity that forces us to do extensive testing for current designs. A better model for load and damage history effects is required; however, a design approach exists which is associated with extensive testing. One of the sound approaches for selecting operating design levels is to utilize the familiar Goodman diagram (see fig. 16) in which vibratory stresses are plotted as a function of steady stresses. Limited experimental data can be fit with curves such as those shown here for several different composites. These enable the designer to translate the sparse data base into the fatigue design conditions which he needs.

In this phase of the discussion, I have attempted to establish the fact that adequate preliminary material design tools exist. It is possible to consider a wide range of material design alternatives and establish the necessary

Figure 15. Statistical strength Distribution Functions for Two Flaw Populations at Different Stages of Lifetime

material properties. We must recognize, however, that the failure mechanisms will be diverse and therefore we must move cautiously. Given the capability to establish material properties, we may then move on to the question of candidate geometric configurations.

STRUCTURAL DESIGN AND ANALYSIS

The design problem is to establish the structural configuration, as well as the material configuration, by considering the type of load, the magnitude of load, fixed structural dimensions, material properties, candidate geometric configurations, and fabrication and cost constraints. The design problem must

Figure 16. Fatigue Data in the Form of a Goodman Diagram for Composites.

have a performance or cost objective. Thus, given these stated design conditions, the designer must find the values for the active design variables, subject to the design constraints. He must optimize for the defined objective. Procedures exist for doing this. They fall under the classifications of structural efficiency. Loads and governing dimensions are defined, alternative structural configurations are postulated, the design limitations are used as guidelines in selecting candidate materials and fabrication processes, and one quantitatively explores these available alternatives. In order to do this effectively for composites, it is necessary to take advantage of the flexibility of the fabrication process. This includes utilization of the following types of concepts: combination of various types of structural elements (and materials) within one structural component; creation of stiffening by using local shell curvatures; utilization of integral, or attached, stiffeners of open or closed section; utilization of area stiffening, such as sandwich plates and shells; etc.

I will illustrate the structural efficiency approach with the simple representative problem shown in figure 17, namely, a cantilever laterally loaded sandwich plate. The core of this sandwich structure is used to repre-

Figure 17. Illustrative Structural Problem.

sent stiffening in general. Such stiffening enables one to spread the major load-carrying material away from the middle plane and thereby to build up the section bending properties for a lateral loading problem. Structural requirements exist in this problem for stiffness to limit deflection, as well as for strength and stability. The available design dimensions are core height and face sheet thickness. These variables define the design space as shown in figure 18. Each of the design constraints, be it stability, strength, or stiffness, divides this space into an acceptable and an unacceptable region. The only acceptable designs are those which satisfy all constraints. The designer's problem is to choose from among these acceptable designs. The procedure for doing this is to plot curves of constant weight, as shown in figure 18. (In this case weight is selected as the illustrative design objective.) The design point is then that point in the design space, in this case point A, which yields the lowest weight design. The design dimensions are then defined and, of course, they depend upon the failure mode constraints, as well as the magnitude of the load levels for the particular problem under consideration. In general, more than one failure mode will influence the final design. The important failure mode will vary depending upon the load intensity. This is illustrated in figure 19, wherein minimum weight curves are plotted as a function of the loading intensity for a composite plate having various laminate configurations. For this simple problem the different failure modes shown yield straight lines on this logarithmic plot. It is apparent that different modes govern at different load intensities. This results in an interchange in the relative merits of the different laminates for different design conditions.

Figure 18. Structural Design Space for Laterally Loaded Sandwich Plate.

Figure 19. Typical Structural Efficiency Chart for Plate Elements.

Figure 20. Torque Tube Design

A more specific example is provided by consideration of a composite torque tube. This torque tube was designed from a laminate whose fibers were oriented along the tube and helically in a symmetric pattern at angles $\pm\theta$ to the axial direction. The required wall thickness, and hence the tube weight, is plotted in figure 20 as a function of the angle θ considering the two major design constraints: static shear strength, and buckling under torsion load. It is seen that the optimum design point, namely the minimum thickness which satisfies both constraints, is a design whose configuration differs from the minimum weight design achieved when only one or the other of the design conditions is selected.

Application of this same logic to the case of complex stiffened skin structures is accomplished by performing the following tasks:

1. Define major load paths.
2. Identify minimum skin requirements.
3. Select desirable elements for each load path.
4. Establish load introduction paths, and attachment concepts.
5. Define stiffening requirements for stability and vibration.
6. Assess interaction between local and overall stiffening needs.
7. Do preliminary sizing.

It is then necessary to appraise the total configuration that results from this process in order to seek changes which will result in a reduction in weight, and more importantly, a reduction in fabrication complexity and total cost. Cost consideration must include not only acquisition costs for the part, but also lifetime costs.

If one returns to the beam design space which we discussed before (see fig. 18) in addition to constant weight functions, it is possible to draw on this same chart constant cost functions (see fig. 21) and to obtain a design in which the minimum cost point will be established. In this case, the minimum cost design is at point C. It is important to emphasize that the minimum cost will be established for different structural dimensions than those associated with the minimum weight design point. This illustrates the important fact that cost considerations must enter into the design at an early stage.

Figure 21. Structural Design Space Including Determination of Minimum Cost Designs.

When we include cost considerations, we must treat not only recurring costs (e.g. labor, material, energy, etc.) and non-recurring costs (e.g. tooling, facilities, etc.) but also it is necessary to introduce the concept of premium. If we have a design objective, be it reduced weight, for example, we must be willing to pay something for that weight reduction. We must quantify the value of achieving that design objective. Thus, in the common case of interest in weight reduction, one introduces a premium which is applied to the weight saving associated with the utilization of composites in this application. That cost savings (which is quantitatively the premium value in \$/lb times the weight saved) reduces the effective cost of the component.

The premium, for one of the exciting areas of current application of composites, namely, the automotive industry, is clearly in the energy savings associated with reduced weight. There is, first of all, an energy savings associated with acquisition costs, as shown in table 2a. This shows the manufacture energy for a representative automotive part made from steel, aluminum and graphite/epoxy. The weights of the competing parts and the total energy are

Table 2. Energy Requirements for Representative Automotive Components

ENERGY SAVINGS

A. EFFECT UPON ACQUISITION COSTS

MATERIAL	WEIGHT (LBS)	MANUFACTURE ENERGY (10^6 BTU)
STEEL	75	2.6
ALUMINUM	37	4.1
GRAPHITE/EPOXY	19	1.4

B. EFFECT UPON IN-SERVICE COSTS

MATERIAL	5-YR. ENERGY USE (10^6 BTU)
STEEL	9.8
ALUMINUM	4.9
GRAPHITE/EPOXY	2.6

shown. It is seen that there is a substantial reduction in the energy associated with the composite. Of equal importance, there is an energy savings associated with in-service costs, which are estimated in table 2b, for five years of automotive use with typical weight savings (from a study done by NASA). Again, there is a reduced energy utilization for graphite composites. This in-service energy saving must be translated into a premium value for equivalent initial acquisition cost. When this is done, the range over which advanced composites become cost effective is greatly enhanced.

The cost savings can be illustrated more specifically with a design example in which we examined the reinforcement of a truck-frame beam made of a steel channel with a uniaxial graphite/epoxy cap applied to both flanges of the beam for bending application (see fig. 22). The cost comparisons between

Figure 22. Selectively Reinforced Truck Frame Beam

the unreinforced steel channel and the uniaxially reinforced steel channel are shown in figure 23. Effective beam cost is shown for a range of manufacturing costs. It is clear that if no premium is paid for weight savings, it is cheaper to utilize the steel construction for practical manufacturing cost ranges. However, when the reduced weight of the hybrid design is valued, in this case at a premium of \$1/lb of weight saved, then the effective cost of the selectively reinforced steel beam is reduced significantly. One can quantitatively establish the cost effectiveness of this selectively reinforced composite as compared to the steel composite. The result is that the hybrid becomes cost effective with respect to the steel. However, the point here is not so much this end result, but rather the fact that the design capability exists to evaluate these alternative configurations on a quantitative cost basis. Indeed, this example emphasizes our general needs and capabilities in the area of combining materials. We must be able to evaluate the relative importance of the different material properties. We must do this because the cost effective utilization of advanced composites will come about by combining them with other materials.

An illustration of the comparison procedure which can be utilized to assess relative material performance is shown in figure 24. In this case we are studying a sandwich plate structure subjected to lateral pressure. The weight index curve (going down to the right) is a plot of the weight of

Figure 23. Cost Comparison Between Steel and Hybrid Beams Including the Effects of Premium for Weight Savings

the structural component as a function of the Young's modulus of the material used in the face sheet of the sandwich plate. Weight savings can be achieved by using materials of higher stiffness to density ratio. However, as the modulus increases, the required strength necessary to achieve this minimum weight configuration also increases. Thus, required strength for any modulus value is shown by the ascending curve. One must trade off the strength versus the modulus. For illustration, two candidate materials are plotted. The first material (point A) has a composite modulus of 15 million psi, and has a strength which is just in excess of that required to enable us to achieve minimum weight. Hence, the true weight obtainable from this design is as given

Figure 24. Comparison of Candidate Materials for Plates Subjected to Lateral Loads

by point C. However, the alternate material (point B) which is a higher modulus material of lower strength, does not have adequate strength to enable us to utilize the potential of the higher modulus in this case. Hence, one must, for this design, return to the strength curve and move to the weight curve at that reduced modulus value (point D). Here it can be seen that the alternative material will have a higher weight than the baseline material. Thus, the improved modulus could not be utilized, even in a modulus sensitive environment, because the strength was inadequate. Again, the emphasis is on the fact that capability exists to perform this trade-off. Indeed this can be done not only on the composite laminate level, but also on the fiber level. Thus one may ask questions for class of applications as to what the desired fiber properties are for a given application, or what the desired laminate properties are, and one can explore ways to achieve these properties using the methods discussed earlier. One result of this approach which we have generalized for a class of automotive applications, namely energy absorbing structural components, such as automobile bumpers, is shown in figure 25. This shows the op-

Figure 25. Utilization of Advanced Composites in Hybrid Form for Energy Absorbing Automotive Structural Elements

timum amount of graphite composite that can be used in a cost effective fashion as a function of the premium for weight savings for the particular application. This fraction of advanced composite will be zero for this application unless there is a premium of approximately \$2/lb of weight saved. When that premium is assigned, there will be cost effective utilization of graphite composites, in this case in conjunction with glass composites. We have found that for practical application, composites in a hybrid configuration, with 5 to 15 or 20% of the composite being graphite/epoxy and the remainder glass/epoxy, represent a very attractive cost effective utilization for composites.

These types of studies enable one to understand what the potential is for utilization of graphite/epoxy composites in one of the most rapidly growing applications for these materials, namely, automobiles. The approach we have used is to take a representative automobile, a 4,000 lb automobile, and to classify the various structural components into the different categories shown

Table 3. Projected Automotive Graphite Fiber Usage

COMPONENT CLASSIFICATION	TOTAL CURRENT WEIGHT	WEIGHT REPLACEMENT FACTOR*
SHEET	1150	0.020-0.055
BEAM	700	0.035
HIGHLY STRESSED	350	0.080
LIGHTLY STRESSED	350	0.045
ENGINE CASTINGS	500	-
NON-STRUCTURAL	950	0
	4000 LBS.	

*RATIO OF GRAPHITE FIBER WEIGHT TO STEEL WEIGHT

in table 3. The estimated current weight breakdown for these components is shown. Design studies of the type shown in this lecture have been performed to find out what type of composite structure would result in a cost effective substitute for the existing metallic structure. The output of such a study is a weight replacement factor, which is the ratio of the graphite fiber weight to the initial steel part weight. It can be seen that this is a relatively low number - a number which ranges in this case from 2 to 8% of the steel part weight. It should be emphasized that this refers only to the amount of graphite fiber. The composite is lighter than the steel part, but a large portion of the composite weight is in the glass composite, and only a small portion is in the graphite composite. Only part of the composite is in the graphite fiber weight. Thus, we have weight replacement factors ranging from 2 to 8% which result in a projected utilization of approximately 100 to 150 lbs of graphite fiber in a cost effective substitute for the structure of this 4,000 lb car. This study has been very valuable in identifying some of the projected design functions projected for automotive applications. It is also believed to be representative of commercial applications of composites in general. Thus, I conclude that advanced composite materials will be used in various combinations with each other and with other materials.

One can foresee various types of sheet molding compounds which will be used with local reinforcement. The sheet molding compounds themselves may be hybrids including some graphite fibers along with glass or Kevlar, or other fibers. They may have preferred fiber orientation of at least one fiber system within the molding compounds. There will be local reinforcement, which is likely to be with graphite or Kevlar fiber tape. There will be some area reinforcement, which is likely to be a fabric of any of the various competing fiber materials. These composites will undoubtedly be developed along with advanced matrix materials. The advancement will not be in the form of higher structural strength and stiffness, but rather in their compatibility with the high production rates which are essential for effective commercial applications. Since the sound approach to utilization of composites is to take a conservative stance in our design capability, the designs which we generate for commercial applications will not require high precision analytical techniques. They will not result from the large scale computer programs for structural analysis. They will rather result from the kinds of intelligent trade-offs which I have tried to describe for you, and which are the available state of the art.

In summary, I would like to stress that a rational evaluation of our capability in the design and analysis of composite materials and structures yields

a positive conclusion. Application of these existing methods emphasizes that advanced fiber composites will be used in combination with each other and with other materials. Hybrids of many materials in many forms will be the long term cost effective products that come from today's technology. The understanding of how these materials behave will continue to grow. The number of people trained to work in this field will increase dramatically. The required R&D investment will come from an increasing number of sources and it will grow larger than it presently is. As a result of all of these facts I believe there will be new freedoms to enable the designer to exercise his ingenuity in development of effective properties. Engineered materials will be common, and over the long term, fiber composites will become a preeminent material of construction.

SESSION IA:
MECHANICAL AND PHYSICAL PROPERTIES-IA

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